

Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment of the Region of Murcia (REGMURCIA CLIMAAX).

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CLIMAAX
climate ready regions

1. INTRODUCTION

The REGMURCIA CLIMAAX project aims to identify the most relevant climate risks affecting the Region of Murcia through a detailed, multi-scale vulnerability assessment. It will be implemented in three phases: initial risk identification using the CLIMAAX methodology, refinement with high-resolution local data, and the development of targeted adaptation measures through stakeholder engagement. Key climate threats include water scarcity, coastal floods, and increasingly frequent fluvial flooding. This initiative is crucial for a region highly exposed to climate impacts. By improving local knowledge and preparedness, REGMURCIA CLIMAAX will support more effective policies and concrete actions to protect people, ecosystems, and the regional economy.

2. REGMURCIA CLIMAAX OBJECTIVES

- Assess current and future climate risks in Murcia, focusing on droughts and fluvial/coastal flooding.
- Apply a three-phase methodology: baseline analysis, local data refinement, and adaptation planning.
- Generate detailed risk and vulnerability maps to guide decision-making.
- Engage stakeholders in developing sector-specific adaptation strategies.
- Enhance institutional capacity through science-based, data-driven planning.

3. REGIONAL CLIMATE RISK SNAPSHOT

The Region of Murcia is one of the most climate-vulnerable areas in southern Europe, due to its semi-arid conditions, geographic exposure, and pressure on natural resources. Extreme events such as heatwaves, prolonged droughts, and severe fluvial flooding—often linked to DANA storms—are becoming more frequent and intense. These risks threaten water security, public health, ecosystems, and key economic sectors, highlighting the urgent need for science-based adaptation and coordinated regional action.

The economic impact of climate risks under different adaptation scenarios. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12207>

Evolution of buildings constructed in flood zones by return period along the CARM coast. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12207>

Escalating Drought Risk in Region of Murcia

Region of Murcia faces an increasingly chronic drought risk, driven by reduced rainfall, aquifer depletion, and rising temperatures. These conditions are straining agriculture, ecosystems, and water supply. Projections indicate worsening scarcity, highlighting the need for adaptive water management and long-term planning.

- Historical drought maps reveal exceptionally low precipitation levels in the Region of Murcia, confirming its high vulnerability to prolonged dry periods.

Growing Exposure to Flood Hazards

Region of Murcia is increasingly vulnerable to fluvial and coastal flooding due to more frequent extreme rainfall and rising sea levels. Urban development in risk zones has amplified impacts, with fewer but more severe events affecting more municipalities. Coastal areas face added threats from storm surges, requiring integrated planning and nature-based solutions.

- Historical flood events in 1972, 1973, and 1989 show extreme rainfall concentrations in southeastern Spain, highlighting the Region of Murcia as a recurrent hotspot.
- Land use under RCP 4.5 for 2050 shows high flood exposure in coastal areas of the Mar Menor, particularly around urban and agricultural zones.

4. REGMURCIA CLIMAAX

REGMURCIA CLIMAAX project is funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe CLIMAAX project (GA which supports regional climate risk assessments across Europe.

REGMURCIA CLIMAAX is a 22-month project that applies the European CLIMAAX methodology to assess key climate risks in the Region of Murcia. It is structured into three main phases:

- **Phase 1** (Months 1–6) focuses on preparing a reference baseline document and applying the CLIMAAX Toolbox to carry out a preliminary multi-risk assessment, resulting in Deliverable 1.
- **Phase 2** (Months 7–14) involves the production of high-resolution technical studies and spatial analyses to refine the regional climate risk profile. This phase culminates in Deliverable 2, a detailed, locally adapted multi-risk assessment.
- **Phase 3** (Months 15–22) emphasizes stakeholder engagement through technical meetings and participatory workshops, leading to the co-design of adaptation strategies and action plans, which are consolidated in Deliverable 3. Throughout the project, scientific analysis is combined with collaborative processes to enhance institutional capacity and integrate climate resilience into regional planning.

Phase	Activity	Duration of the project implementation (22 months)																					
		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22
Phase 1	Preparation of a reference document																						
	Use of the CLIMAAX Toolbox																						
Phase 2	Preparation of the analysis and key risks assessment (deliverable 1)																						
	Technical meetings																						
Phase 3	Specific technical studies or high-resolution maps																						
	Preparation of the refined regional multi-risk assessment (deliverable 2)																						
	Meetings with interested parties																						
	Participatory workshops with stakeholders																						
	Proposed action plans (deliverable 3)																						

5. PRELIMINARY RESULTS (Phase 1)

All packages of TOOLBOX already working. Playing with scenarios and models. Here some examples for Flood and Drought hazards and associated risks.

- Projected flood maps and impact models for Murcia show increasing flood depths and economic damages under climate change scenarios, particularly in urban and high-exposure zones by 2080.

River floods

Droughts

- Projected precipitation deficits under RCP8.5 (2046–2050) in the Region of Murcia are expected to cause significant yield and revenue losses in key crops such as barley and potatoes, particularly in areas with low irrigation coverage.

- Under future climate scenarios, the number of heatwave days is projected to rise sharply—especially under RCP8.5—leading to increased heat risk in densely populated urban areas, where exposure and vulnerability converge.

Heat waves

6. NEXT STEPS

- Finalize the baseline risk assessment using the CLIMAAX Toolbox, integrating regional data and expert validation.
- Launch high-resolution technical studies and spatial analyses to refine the multi-risk assessment (Phase 2).
- Initiate structured stakeholder engagement to guide the co-design of adaptation strategies in the final project phase (Phase 3).

REFERENCES

- Pérez-Morales, A., Gil-Guirado, S., & Olcina-Cantos, J. (2018). Housing bubbles and the increase of flood exposure. Failures in flood risk management on the Spanish south-eastern coast (1975–2013). *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 11, S302-S313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12207>